

Fracture Mechanism of Short Glass Fiber Reinforced Polyamide Thermoplastics

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ABSTRACT

The fracture of short glass fiber reinforced polyamide 6.6 thermoplastics was studied by means of microscopic and acoustic emission measurements. The occurrence of interfacial cracks at the fiber/matrix interface was observed in almost all tensile load ranges, but the matrix cracks were observed just prior to the failure of the composite. The acoustic emissions observed during loading could be classified into two types according to the amplitude. The lower and higher amplitude signals are considered to correspond to the interfacial cracking and the matrix cracking, respectively. In order to analyze the stresses in the matrix, the fiber, and the interface, calculation based on the Eshelby's theory was made. The results are found to support the mechanism of the fracture, the occurrence of the interfacial cracking followed by the matrix cracking.

INTRODUCTION

Short fiber reinforced thermoplastics are being applied to the automobile industry because of the ease of fabrication, weight saving, and economical reasons. For the application, the reliability in the mechanical properties of the composites is one of the most important factors. The fracture mechanism of the composites has been discussed analytically by several workers (1, 2), but some aspects of the mechanism have been left not clarified.

In the present work, experimental and theoretical studies of the short fiber reinforced thermoplastics have been undertaken to improve our understanding of the fracture mechanism.

EXPERIMENTS

Specimens

The material used in this study is thermoplastic polyamide 6.6 reinforced with short glass fibers. The tensile test specimens conforming to the specification of ASTM D638 were molded with a screw-preplasticizing injection molding machine. The volume fraction of fibers in the specimens was in the range from 0.026 to 0.25. The mean length of fibers was about 0.4 mm and, therefore, the

aspect ratio was about 30. Short fibers embedded in the matrix were aligned mainly along the resin flow direction.

Measurement

Specimens were subjected to tensile test at room temperature at a strain rate of 1.7×10^{-4} /sec on an Instron-type machine. The tensile stress was applied along the resin flow direction. The acoustic emission monitoring system was used simultaneously to observe the failure behavior of the specimens. In the monitoring, the amplitude distribution analyzer was also used to classify the signals according to their amplitudes. In order to observe the crack initiation and the fracture surfaces, a reflection optical microscopy and a scanning electron microscopy were used.

STRESS ANALYSIS

The stresses applied to the composite were evaluated by Eshelby's equivalent inclusion methods (3) and Mori-Tanaka's back stress analysis (4), on the assumptions that all the fibers are discontinuous, uniform in length and aligned in the loading direction. From the theory, the stress in the matrix and fiber, σ_{ij}^M and σ_{ij}^F , can be obtained as follows (5),

$$\sigma_{ij}^M = C_{ijkl} \{ \epsilon_{kl}^A - v(S_{klmn} \epsilon_{mn}^T - \epsilon_{kl}^T) \} \quad (1)$$

$$\sigma_{ij}^F = C_{ijkl}^* \{ \epsilon_{kl}^A + (1-v)S_{klmn} \epsilon_{mn}^T + v\epsilon_{kl}^T \} \quad (2)$$

, where C_{ijkl}^* , C_{ijkl} are elastic moduli of the fiber and matrix, respectively, v is the volume fraction of fibers, and ϵ_{kl}^A is the uniform strain due to the applied stress σ_{ij}^A . Therefore, $\sigma_{ij}^A = C_{ijkl} \epsilon_{kl}^A$. In Eqs. (1) and (2), ϵ_{kl}^T is called the "eigenstrain" and is obtained from the following equations,

$$C_{ijkl}^* \{ \epsilon_{kl}^A + (1-v)\epsilon_{kl}^C + v\epsilon_{kl}^T \} = C_{ijkl} \{ \epsilon_{kl}^A + (1-v)(\epsilon_{kl}^C - \epsilon_{kl}^T) \} \quad (3)$$

$$\epsilon_{ij}^C = S_{ijkl} \epsilon_{kl}^T \quad (4)$$

, where S_{ijkl} is Eshelby's tensor which is determined by the aspect ratio of the fiber and Poisson's ratio of the matrix.

Now, the tangential shear stress at the elliptical fiber/matrix interface will be estimated, since the theory assumes the shape of the short fiber to be an ellipsoid. It can be calculated from the stress in the fiber by appropriate transformation of the co-ordinates. The tangential shear stress $\tau(\theta)$ at the interface due to the applied tensile stress is obtained by

$$\tau(\theta) = \frac{1}{2} \sin 2\theta (\sigma_{33}^F - \sigma_{11}^F) \quad (5)$$

, where σ_{33}^F and σ_{11}^F are the longitudinal and transverse stress components in the fiber, respectively, and θ is the inclination angle of the interface against the loading direction. When $\theta = \pi/4$, the shear stress has a maximum value τ_{\max} given as,

$$\tau_{\max} = \frac{1}{2} (\sigma_{33}^F - \sigma_{11}^F) \quad (6)$$

RESULTS

Acoustic Emission

Fig. 1 shows a typical example of AE counts obtained from a specimen with 0.16 volume fraction of fibers. The stress-strain curve is also shown. Acoustic emission began to occur at loads as small as about one fourth of the maximum load and remarkably increased towards the maximum load. In order to analyze AE signals, the amplitude distributions for various levels of loading were taken until the specimen fractured. The result is shown in Fig. 2. There was one peak (51 dB) in the amplitude distribution diagrams for the range of 60 to 90 % of the maximum load. However, a striking distinction was observed in

Fig. 1 AE counts and stress-strain curve.

Fig. 2 Amplitude distribution

Photo. 1 (a): Interfacial crack in fiber end, (b): Interfacial and matrix crack, (c): Matrix crack observed after failure of the composite

the load range of 90 to 95 %, where higher amplitude events (63 dB) appeared in addition to lower amplitude events. At the final load range, only higher amplitude events were observed. These two amplitude events suggest that two different mechanisms are involved in the fracture of the composite.

Microscopic Observation

To observe the crack initiation and propagation, the specimens during loading were observed by an optical microscopy. Photo.1(a) shows a typical example of a composite under a load of about a half of the maximum load, which indicates interfacial crack initiation in the fiber end. As the applied load was increased, the crack was observed to propagate along the interfaces of fiber side. The progressive interfacial cracking under a load of about 90 % of the maximum load was shown in Photo. 1(b). Small matrix cracks were found to occur prior to the failure of the composite. After the failure, many matrix cracks were observed, particularly beneath the fracture surface (Photo. 1(c)). The matrix cracks were observed to initiate from the interfaces and propagate almost perpendicularly to the tensile direction. No fiber breakage was observed in the specimens.

Photo. 2 shows the fracture surface examined by SEM. Most of the fibers were pulled out and the fiber surfaces were covered with thin matrix films.

(a)

(b)

Photo.2 Fracture surface examined by SEM

Calculated result

For the composite subjected to a tensile stress σ_{33}^A along the fiber axis, the tensile stresses in the matrix σ_{33}^M and in the fiber σ_{33}^F and the maximum shear stress at the interface τ_{max} were calculated. The material constants used for the calculation are as follows; Young's modulus = 250 kg/mm², Poisson's ratio = 0.4, for the matrix; Young's modulus = 7000 kg/mm², Poisson's ratio = 0.23 for the fiber; aspect ratio of fibers = 30. The relative stress, the ratio of the calculated stress to the applied one, was calculated. Therefore, the stress levels in individual phases (matrix, fiber, and interface), at which the composite fails, can be estimated by multiplying the relative stress by the failure strength of the composite. The results are shown in Table 1 for the composites of various volume fractions of fibers. From the table, an interesting fact can be noted. The stress level of matrix at the failure is nearly equal to the yielding stress of unfilled polyamide 6.6 (5.6 kg/mm²) and the stress level of fiber is a half of the fiber strength (200-250 kg/mm²). The maximum shear stress level of the interface is about several times of the fiber/matrix shear bond strength (6.5 kg/mm²)(1). The results indicate that the interfacial crack will initiate under a relatively low load. The matrix crack due to the yielding will occur near the maximum load. No fiber breakage can be considered to occur even at the maximum load.

DISCUSSION

The following model for the fracture mechanism of the composite can be proposed from the experimental and theoretical investigations. First, a number of cracks initiate at the fiber ends under a certain load. As the load increases, the cracks propagate in the matrix along the interfaces, leaving a thin film on the fibers. This interfacial cracking is not caused by the fiber/matrix debonding. Second, matrix cracks grow from the interfacial cracks just prior to the failure of the composite. The catastrophic crack propagation in the matrix leads to the final failure of the composite. Even in this stage, fibers are only pulled out from the matrix without being broken.

Examination of the relation between the occurrence of AE signals and the cracks observed by the microscopy at the same load range reveals that AE signals can be related to the two separate crack initiations. The lower amplitude signals observed below 95 % of the maximum load are considered to be due to the occurrence of the interfacial damage. The higher amplitude signals observed near the failure load are considered to be due to that of the matrix crack. And the analysis based on this interpretation of the AE signals supports the proposed fracture mechanism.

Table 1 Failure strength of composites (experimental value), relative stresses, and stress levels in individual phases at composite failure (calculated value).

volume fraction (%)	failure strength (kg/mm ²)	relative stress			stress level at failure (kg/mm ²)		
		matrix	fiber	interface	matrix	fiber	interface
2.6	8.6	0.67	14	7.0	5.8	120	60
6.6	9.2	0.42	9.2	4.6	3.8	85	42
12.2	13.8	0.28	6.2	3.1	3.9	86	43
16	17.2	0.22	4.9	2.5	3.8	84	43
20.6	19.4	0.17	4.2	2.1	3.3	81	41
25	22	0.16	3.5	1.8	3.5	77	40

The theoretical analysis showed that a significant interfacial damage will initiate at a relatively low load. And the stress level of the matrix at the failure of the composite is nearly equal to its yielding stress. Occurrence of matrix cracking without being accompanied by the matrix yielding may be due to the notch effect made by the interfacial damage and the suppression of the matrix flow by the adjacent fibers. This may explain the brittle manner of the composite failure, in contrast with the ductility of the unfilled polymer. It has been also confirmed that the fiber embedded in the matrix will not break at the failure. These theoretical results are considered to be consistent with the experimental observations.

CONCLUSION

In the short glass fiber reinforced polyamide 6.6 under a tensile load, the interfacial crack initiates at the fiber end and the progressive crack follows along the interface. Prior to the failure of the composite, the matrix crack occurs from the interfacial damage, but no fiber breakage occurs even at the failure of the composite. AE signals due to their cracking could be classified according to the amplitude. The theoretical stress analysis supports the fracture mechanism mentioned above.

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